

DEPRESSION DETECTION USING DEEP LEARNING

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Abstract— Depression is a mental disorder that affects more than 300 million people worldwide. An individual suffering from depression functions poorly in life, is prone to other diseases and in the worst-case, depression leads to suicide. There are many impediments that prevent expert care from reaching people suffering from depression in time. Impediments such as social stigma associated with mental disorders, lack of trained health-care professionals and ignorance of the signs of depression owing to a lack of awareness of the disease. Moreover, the World Health Organization (WHO) claims that individuals who are depressed are often not correctly diagnosed and others who are misdiagnosed are prescribed antidepressants. Thus, there is a strong need to automatically assess the risk of depression. Identification of depression from social media has been framed as a classification problem in the field of Natural Language Processing (NLP). In this work NLP an approach has been studied which can successfully extract information from textual data to enhance identification of depression. These NLP approaches perform feature extraction in order to build document representations. The issues of detecting depression in a social media environment are data scarcity for users with depression and the inherent noise associated with social media data. We attempt to address those issues by using representations that can naturally cope with a social media environment. Specifically, we propose the usage of Distributed Term Representations (DTRs) to capture information that can be used by supervised machine learning methods- Logistic Regression, Naive

Bayes for learning and classifying users suffering from depression.

Index Terms: Deep learning, Machine Learning

I. INTRODUCTION

Social media platforms increasingly come closer to become a true digitization of the human social experience. In many cases people would in fact prefer to express themselves online than off-line. A study by Marriott and Buchanan [18] shows that there is no significant difference between an individual's online personality and off-line personality in terms of authenticity. In the aforementioned study an individual's online personality refers to the personality traits that can be inferred from their social media activity. Whereas, the off-line personality is what people think they are as an individual self. Moreover, there is a tremendous growth in number of users for social media platforms. 81 of a social media profile as of the year 2017. Owing to the factors discussed above it has become possible to infer health related risks of people from social media platforms. In the study by Paul and Dredze [25] the authors attempt to answer the question what public health information could be learned from twitter? They have found that depression is one of the most common ailments that can be associated to a certain group of words. Another study by Park et al. [23] shows through structured interviews that users suffering from depression perceive twitter as a place for social awareness and emotional interaction. In this work when we refer to depression we mean Major Depressive Disorder (MDD) [7]. An

individual may be suffering from depression if they show signs of extreme irritability, anger, loss of interest in favorite activities, constant regret, thoughts of death or suicide, aches or pains, headaches, cramps or digestive problems without a clear physical cause over a period of at least two weeks. The risk factors or potential causes of depression are personal or family history of depression, major life changes, trauma or stress, certain physical illnesses and medications. It is not uncommon for users on social media platforms to share major life changes, factors that caused stress and in fewer cases indicate that they are physically ill. The primary aim of early detection of depression is identifying users showing signs of depression so that appropriate diagnosis and treatment may follow at the earliest. Depression if untreated may lead to undesirable effects apart from the disease itself, such as increased chances of risky behavior like drug or alcohol addiction, make it difficult to recover from other serious illnesses and the disease itself may be prolonged for years viz clinical depression. Dysthymia is a different depression disorder which has a prolonged impact but is less severe than MDD. The numbers are quite disturbing as there are approximately 322 million people suffering from depression disorders worldwide and this number is expected to grow larger by the year [22]. There are many barriers that stand against proper health care. Barriers such as social stigma associated with mental disorders and lack of trained health care providers. Additionally, the larger fraction of people suffering from depression are from low-income countries so this affects likelihood of these 2 people receiving expert care. Clearly there is a strong need to tackle depression by identifying risks as soon as possible using social media platforms. Identifying depressed people online can pave the way for locating and helping people who need professional care but do not have access to them owing to the aforementioned barriers.

1.0.2 Research Goal

Research goal is “To adapt textual representations that can improve the state of-threat in early detection of depression”. In this work we use Natural Language Processing (NLP) approaches to extract information from

textual data. Information that can improve the identification of social media users who are suffering from depression using supervised machine learning approaches. Our major contributions towards depression detection are stated as follows:

We propose the usage of various Distributed Term Representations (DTRs) to capture and naturally encode useful information from text that can enhance identification of users with depression. • We compare NLP approaches that have been proven effective for text classification in the depression detection and author-profiling literature. • We show that user specific DTRs are more effective for depression detection than traditional approaches such as Bag of Words (BOW) and approaches based on neural word embeddings such as A Simple Representation for Documents , Learning the Differences in Word Usage

3 The following is an outline of the manuscript:

- Chapter 2 - Literature Review: This chapter discusses other relevant work from the depression detection literature.
- Chapter 3 - Theoretical Background: This chapter discusses the required background in order to grasp further chapters.
- Chapter 4 - Methodology: This chapter describes how the problem of identifying depression is formulated and presents our overall approach along with approaches that exploit textual data.
- Chapter 5 - Data: This chapter explains how data was collected for experimental evaluation and provides necessary details regarding the nature of the dataset.
- Chapter 6 - Experimental Evaluation: This chapter presents the objectives, experimental settings and relevant discussion about the results that follow from experiments.
- Chapter 7 - General Conclusions: This chapter states the conclusions that can be drawn from the entire work.

2.0 Literature survey

In this chapter we discuss relevant work on identifying signs of depression from social media. Then we provide insight about the direction of research in depression detection along with our proposed approach

2.1 Statistical methods based Approaches

A majority of the work on identifying depression from social media attempts at making the process of diagnosing individuals automatic or semi-automatic. These works do not try to replace psychologists but they attempt to provide a beneficial tool to ease their clinical burden. These works are primarily based on statistical methods. Collecting relevant statistics by quantifying activity on social media platforms, standard psychometric measures, positive or negative emotions, social isolation and social media platform specific statistics. By platform specific statistics we mean statistics based on the number of followers or friends on twitter, the network of users based on user interests or mutual connections. Noteworthy works that fall into this category are De Choudhury et al. [5] in which statistical models were used to characterize differences between mothers with Postpartum Depression (PD) and mothers without PD. PD is a mood disorder that can affect mothers after childbirth. Facebook data was collected from 165 volunteers during prenatal and postnatal periods to predict likelihood of PD. The ground truth was formulated based on volunteer self-reports and PHQ-9 (Patient Health Questionnaire-9) a standard psychometric measure. The statistics the authors based their predictions on belong to four categories: (i) user characteristics; number of facebook status updates, income, age, entropy of activity etc. (ii) social capital; number of likes on facebook status updates, comments on uploaded media, wall posts by friends etc. (iii) content characteristics; positive and negative emotion affect measures using LIWC (Linguistic Inquiry and Word Count) tool, number of posts which are questions. (iv) linguistic style; usage of articles, verbs, conjunctions, adverbs and personal pronouns etc but the model was based on data from the entire prenatal period plus one month from the postnatal period and the model successfully explains 48% in the data. The best predictive variables were variables that quantified user interaction on facebook from the user characteristics category and social capital variables. In De Choudhury et al. [4] authors have used crowd-sourcing to obtain user data from twitter. They successfully collected data for 476 users. Users were

categorized as depressed based on CES-D 6 (Center for Epidemiological Studies Depression Scale) questionnaire, questions about depression history and demographics. The authors have proposed usage of numerous measures to predict the likelihood of depression before it effects the user viz before onset of depression. For this purpose they used one year of twitter activity prior to onset of depression for users who were depressed. The measures that were used to build feature vectors can be categorized as follows: (i) engagement; normalized number of posts per day, fraction of re-tweets per day, number of posts which are questions etc. (ii) egocentric graph measures; a graph based on the social media graph but limited to a two-hop neighborhood. (iii) emotion; positive and negative emotion affect measures using LIWC (Linguistic Inquiry and Word Count) tool. (iv) linguistic style; usage of articles, verbs, conjunctions, adverbs and personal (v) language; a lexicon of words likely to appear among users with depression and noting the presence of antidepressant names. Using the above measures the authors designed feature vectors. The authors then utilized Principal Component Analysis (PCA) [10] to reduce the dimensionality of the feature vectors. The authors then proceeded to use the reduced feature vectors to train a Support Vector Machine which obtained an accuracy of 70% on a 10-fold cross validation. Finally, in the work by Park et al. [24] authors intend to develop a web application “emotion diary” to identify features from 7 facebook that can be related to symptoms of depression. They recruited 55 users (40 males, 15 females, mean age 24.43) through advertisements. Using the emotion diary application users’ facebook activity was monitored and users’ responses to various tips and facts about depression were recorded. The ground truth was based on responses to Center for Epidemiological Studies-Depression (CES-D) scale which is a standard psychometric measure. The authors then performed a correlation analysis between CES-D and the responses of users to tips and facts about depression. They also performed a correlation analysis between CES-D and features that quantified facebook activity. The authors found that number of application tips viewed and application points had a positive

correlation ($P=.04$ for both) with the CES-D scale. Whereas, the number of friends and location tags on facebook had a negative correlation with the CES-D scale ($P=.08$ and $P=.045$ respectively). When attempting to find group differences between probably depressed (CES-D 25) and probably non-depressed groups they found that the number of application tips viewed and application points resulted in significant differences ($P=.01$ and $P=.03$ respectively). This correlation analysis demonstrated that users who are depressed will have probably reduced activity on facebook and will view more tips and facts about depression. The major drawback of this study is the limited population the authors have chosen. Moreover, all the participants are students about the same age from a Korean University.

2.0.2 Natural Language Processing Approaches

Unlike the works mentioned in section 2.1 our aim is to detect the risk of depression solely from natural language and raise awareness of it so that treatment could begin. This is a far more practical approach than collecting detailed statistics for every user as in reality it is not possible to obtain information such as standard psychometric measures for all users on a social media platform. In 2016 Nadeem [21] used a Bag of Words (BOW) approach for each tweet on twitter to classify users with depression and obtained an accuracy of 81% on a 6-fold cross validation. This was a progressive step as it attempts to tackle depression detection using natural language only but there is a notable limitation of this work. The users who were considered depressed for evaluation purposes (dataset from CL Psych 2015 shared task) were ones who simply claimed on twitter that they were depressed. The dataset that was used for evaluation purpose in our work is from the eRisk 11 2017 shared task. It was prepared by Losada and Crestani [14] from reddit. The users that have been categorized as belonging to the depressed class are individuals who have voluntarily disclosed medical information that they have been diagnosed with depression. In the shared task Trozsek et al. [27] proposed five models for depression detection: (i) Model named BCSGA which can be summarized as an ensemble of BOW based on hand crafted features. (ii) Model named BCSGB which is

based on computing document representations using a well-known technique doc2vec [12]. (iii) A Long Term Short Term Memory (LSTM) network [9] based model called BCSGC which uses Latent Semantic Analysis (LSA) [6] vectors for training. (iv) A LSTM model called BCSGD that uses paragraph vectors from doc2vec for training. (v) A LSTM model called BCSGE which is a late LSTM network that was trained both on train and test data. It was an unsupervised learning technique. BCSGA was the approach that had the highest F1 score of 0.63 on the depressed class at eRisk 2017. Usage of hand crafted features in models like BCSGA has undesirable limitations such as dependence on domain experts and incompleteness as the same hand-crafted features may not produce similar performance on other datasets. The other participating systems which obtained runner-up positions at eRisk 12 2017 [15] are the LIDIC research group from Universidad Nacional de San Luis and participants from University of Quebec in Montreal, Canada. The LIDIC research group used a semantic representation of documents that had the capability to consider partial information viz incomplete documents. They used multiple document representations such as BOW, Concise Semantic Analysis (CSA) [13], representations based on character 3-grams and features from the LIWC (Linguistic Inquiry and Word Count) toolkit. They used classification methods such as decision trees, random forests and Naive Bayes classifier and obtained an F1 score of 0.59 on the depressed class. Participants from University of Quebec, developed a predictive system that utilized a combination of ensemble classification and information retrieval. Their feature extraction involved usage of n-grams, dictionary words, part-of-Speech tags and user posting frequency. The information retrieval component of the system considered a test document as a query and searched for similar documents. Two kinds of search engines were built from the training set each with its own different data preprocessing scheme. The ensemble classification component of the system combined predictions of multiple classifiers with different configurations. Finally, a decision algorithm merged the predictions from the information retrieval component and

ensemble classification component. They obtained F1 score of 0.53 on the depressed class.

2.0.3 Proposed Approach and Discussion

Depression detection via social media is still a burgeoning research area. A work on identifying suicidal ideologies from social media [3] suggests a rather unique approach using Computer Networks or graph-based techniques to group users with suicidal ideologies. In the work by Park et al. [23] authors suggest a redesign of social networks which could simplify identification depressed users. Since current works for depression detection uses methods from NLP, Computer Networks, future research may involve a combination of methods from NLP and Computer Networks. In our work we propose usage of existing Distributional Term Representations (DTRs) and a newly adapted DTR to build enriched feature representations to classify depressed users. DTRs represent terms by means of contextual information from document occurrence and term co-occurrence statistics. DTRs have attractive properties such as lower dimensionality, better interpretability and higher discriminative power as opposed to traditional approaches like BOW. We also attempt using neural word embeddings like word2vec to build existing and new document representations. word2vec embeddings have been proven to capture semantic relationships among words [20]. Considering the numerous approaches to tackle depression detection and that have been discussed so far in this chapter it is easy to see that there has been lot of valuable effort poured into this research area. Unfortunately even though this is the 14 case current methods are not sufficient to deploy a depression detection system on a large scale for even one specific social media platform. The current methods definitely need to improve in terms of accuracy and these methods need to generalize well over different kinds of data. The ideal depression detection system would possess a fully automated learning capability to capture signs of depression for users across any social media platform with an acceptable level of accuracy and report the necessary details of depressed users within an appropriate period.

3.0. Theoretical background

In this chapter we explain concepts from Natural Language Processing which are necessary to grasp the proceeding chapters. Readers who are already familiar with Bag of Words and Word Embeddings are encouraged to skip this chapter entirely. Additionally, the manuscript also presumes that the reader is well acquainted with Supervised Machine Learning methods which are used for classification problems.

3.1 Bag of Words

Let $D = \{d_1, d_2, \dots, d_n\}$ be a set of documents. In general each document consists of textual data or in our case a collection of posts written by a user. Usually a document or a different representation of the document is considered as a single training instance while training a classifier. Bag of Words is a method by which we can arrive at a representation $d_i \in D$ based on occurrences of tokens (words and other atomic 16 entities) in each document. Let $V = \{t_1, t_2, \dots, t_m\}$ be the set of unique tokens that occur in D viz the entire corpus. Then the Bag of Words representation for a document d_i is a vector of size m , $\langle f_1, f_2, \dots, f_m \rangle$ where f_i is the frequency of token t_i in document d_i . So the resulting representation for D is a matrix of dimensions $n \times m$. There are notable variations of Bag of Words where different values are used for each entry in the above matrix instead of using the raw frequencies. For example, in Binary Bag of Words we simply place a 1 in each entry when a token occurs in a document and 0 when the token is not present in a document. Another common variation is to pass the raw frequencies (f) through a function $g(f)$. Commonly used candidates for $g(f)$ are $g_1(f) = 1 + \log_2(f)$ and $g_2(f) = g_1(f) \times \log\left(\frac{n}{n_t}\right)$ where n_t is the number of documents in which token t occurs. The latter viz $g_2(f)$ is from the field of information retrieval and it is termed as tf-idf (term frequency - inverse document frequency). In some cases it maybe beneficial to exclude some tokens by considering a subset of tokens $S \subseteq V$ to compute the Bag of Words representation.

3.2 Word Embeddings

The meaning of a word can be inferred based on the words that are distributed around it or simply the neighboring words. Consider the following sentences, "Hail Krishna !", "Down south there is a temple dedicated to Krishna". From the

distribution of words around Krishna it is possible to infer that Krishna refers to a deity. The field of vector semantics in Natural Language Processing (NLP) is dedicated to modeling words by representing them in a vector space. Since words are embedded into a vector space the vector representation of a word is called a word embedding. There are two kinds of vector representations sparse and dense. Sparse vectors are computed using various methods from a term-document matrix over a corpus. For example, the vector 12 representation we arrived at in section 3.1 is a sparse representation as the dimensionality of vectors is proportional to the size of the vocabulary V (usually $|V| = 50,000$). Moreover, in practice not all terms in V occur in each document so most of the entries in the term-document matrix are zeros. On the contrary dense vector representations are of lower dimensions (50-1000) and mostly have non-zero values. They are computed by using one of the following techniques, (i) dimensionality reduction methods like Singular Value Decomposition [6] (ii) using neural networks like skip-gram or CBOW (Continuous Bag of Words) (iii) brown clustering [2]. The word embeddings that are used in this work are word2vec (w2v) embeddings that are computed using neural networks based on the work by Mikolov et al. [20]

4.0 Methodology

In this chapter we first describe our approach to identify depression from social media. Then we provide an overview of our system and the pipeline of various stages that comprise the system. Subsequent sections explain the various methods by which we extracted useful information from textual data. The problem of identifying users with depression from their posts on social media has been formulated as a classification problem. The target classes being depressed and non-depressed. There are two scenarios in which classification can be performed namely early and non-early or full-text. In the full-text scenario the problem is a standard classification problem where the depression detection system is required to simply predict whether a user belongs to the depressed class or the non-depressed class.

Whereas, in the early scenario the system needs to minimize the number of posts it uses during the testing phase. The system is in fact penalized for utilizing more posts by the Early Risk Detection Error (ERDE) metric [15]. The term ‘early’ is logically coherent as the posts of users are ordered chronologically. So when the depression detection system uses fewer posts to output a prediction, it is actually making a decision earlier in time. It is desirable to make early 14 decisions (without compromising on accuracy) so that users suffering from depression could receive treatment before the symptoms of depression grow more severe. The challenging aspects of the problem are the inherent noise that is associated with social media data, Unbalanced Data Set (UDS) and Classification on Partial Information (CPI). UDS refers to the fact that the number of users belonging to the depressed class are in minority when compared to the number of users belonging to the nondepressed class. UDS poses additional challenges for machine learning algorithms. It especially makes it harder for supervised machine learning algorithms to learn and predict depressed class users. CPI refers to the requirement of the depression detection system to output predictions based on partial information that is currently available. Consider Table 4.1, Bob is a depressed user whereas Alice is a non-depressed user. Further, assume that the trained system receives as input at any time step a single post in the order Post1, Post2 and Post3 in order to make a prediction. Note that, the system can and should utilize information seen in the previous time step along with new information available at the current step. The CPI issue in the case of Bobble 4.1: Illustration of Classification on Partial Information (CPI) with trivial input. Bob is a user suffering from depression whereas Alice is a non-depressed user. The numbered posts represent information available during early evaluation in chronological 15 order. is if the system fails to predict that he is depressed after seeing Post1 and Post2 and waits until it receives Post3 it will be penalized. So the prediction was given too late in the case of Bob. Similarly, in the case of Alice if the system predicts that she is depressed before receiving Post3 as input it would result in a false positive. So in the case

of Alice the prediction was made too early. The problem can be mathematically formulated as follows, let $U = u_1, u_2, \dots, u_n$ be a set of users and let $D = d_1, d_2, \dots, d_n$ be a set of documents written by corresponding users in U . Each document, $d_i \in D$ is a collection of posts made by a user on a social media platform. Therefore, the aim is to map all $u_i \in U$ to one of the target classes, $T = \text{depressed}, \text{non-depressed}$ as soon as possible. We propose to achieve the aforementioned goal by extracting information that is useful to categorize users from the text present in the documents. Figure 4.1: System Pipeline for full-text scenario (left) and early scenario (right). In both scenarios, the first three phases are equivalent. In the full-text scenario the system performs standard classification and the classifier's decision is final whereas, in the early scenario a policy determines the final decision. The stages that comprise the system are shown in Figure 4.1. The first stage involves application of data preprocessing techniques on the set of documents available for training. Thereafter, we perform feature extraction by computing a document representation for each preprocessed document. Note that, each document is equivalent to a single training instance and a document representation is equivalent to a feature vector that is used to represent a training instance. We then train a classifier using the document representations and use this classifier to predict the target class for users during evaluation. In both the full-text and early scenario documents of test users are represented using the same method which was used to compute document representations during training. In the full-text scenario the final output of the system is the prediction made by the classifier. Whereas, in the early scenario there is a need for a postprocessing stage. The post-processing consists of a policy which determines whether the current prediction for a user made by the classifier is the final prediction for the user or not. For example, the policy we have used involves checking whether the probability of a user belonging to the depressed class say $P_{\text{depressed}}$ is above a fixed threshold value, th . If $P_{\text{depressed}} > th$ then we can confidently predict that the user belongs to the depressed

class and the system no longer consumes test data for this user. Different kinds policies can be defined and implemented although designing an efficient policy is quite challenging as it directly affects performance in the early scenario. Our major contribution involves proposing the usage of effective document representations based on Distributional Term Representations (DTRs) and word embeddings for depression detection. Distributional Term Representations (DTRs) such as Document Occurrence Representation and Concise Semantic Analysis have been successfully used for the tasks of author-profiling and short-text categorization. On the other hand Word embeddings are used almost ubiquitously in NLP. They are used more often in conjunction with deep learning models and in situations where there is a need to capture semantics or word similarity. The following sections describe existing and novel approaches that have been used to compute document representations

4.0 Logistic regression and Naive Bayes algorithm

Logistic regression is the classical and the best bicategorical algorithm which is preferred when dealing with classification problems, especially bicategorical ones. The choice of algorithm is based on the principle of simplicity before complexity. Logistic regression is also an excellent choice because it is a recognised statistical method used to predict the outcome of a binomial or polynomial. A multinomial logistic regression algorithm can regenerate the model. It will be a better classification algorithm when the target field or data is a set field with two or more possible values. The advantage of logistic regression is that he is faster to process and is suitable for bicategorical problems. It is also more straightforward for any beginner to understand and directly see the weights of each feature. Then it is easier to update the model and incorporate new data for different problems (Aihua et al. 2007). Furthermore, it has a disadvantage. There is a limit to the data and the adaptability of the scene. Not as adaptable as the decision tree algorithm. But this is an issue that we can also determine in this project based on the actual situation

whether the logistic regression has a better ability to adapt to an extensive data set (Ng and Jordan 2002). The main methods of logistic regression method: Objective: To predict the user is depressed or not, then in this project, we want to process depression dataset individual variable data to predict the dependent variable data for finding depressed user. Prediction: Predicting the probability of positive and negative word under other independent variables, based on different algorithmic models. Judgment: It is somewhat 19 similar to prediction. It is also based on different models to see the input characters is positive or negative, how likely it is that user input characters is a falls into a positive or negative category. Regression General Steps Finding the h-function (i.e., the prediction function) Constructing the predictive function $h(x)$, the logistic function, or also known as the sigmoid function, we generally the first step is to build the predictive process, where the training data for the vector, as well as the best parameters. Constructing the loss function The second step is that we need to construct the loss function-j. In general, there will be m samples, each with n characteristics. The Cost and J functions are as follows, and they are derived based on maximum likelihood estimation(Sahin and Duman 2011). Naive Bayes Algorithm An alternate way of calculating the conditional probability of an event. When the reverse conditional probability is easier to calculate than the joint probability, Bayes' Theorem is used Naive Bayes assumes conditional independence over the training dataset. The classifier separates data into different classes according to the Bayes' Theorem. But assumes that the relationship between all input features in a class is independent. Naive Bayes
$$P(A|x_1, \dots, x_n) = P(x_1|A).P(x_2|A).P(x_i|A)P(A)$$

5.0 DATA

In this chapter we first describe the dataset that was used for experimental evaluation. Then we explain the data preprocessing techniques that were employed.

5.1 Dataset Description

The dataset we have used is prepared by

Losada and Crestani [14]. The data has been collected from the social media platform reddit. This dataset has been utilized in the “eRisk 2017” [15] challenge. The users that were considered to be depressed were users who explicitly mentioned on reddit that they were diagnosed with depression. Posts such as “I have depression”, “I think I have depression”, or “I am depressed” were not considered as depressed. Only posts such as “In 2013, I was diagnosed with depression” and “After struggling with depression for many years, yesterday I was diagnosed” were considered as posts of users suffering from depression. The reddit 36 users with such posts were followed up with strict manual reviews for the purpose of authenticity and only then they were considered to be users belonging to the depressed class. The dataset consists of two partitions train and test. Both the train and test

Partitions are further divided into 10 subdivisions called “chunks”. A chunk contains a set of documents each written by a single user. A document can be defined as a collection of posts written by a user. The documents are organized into chunks in such a way that a chronological order is maintained. For example, all documents in chunk1 contain posts that were written earlier in time than the ones written in chunk2 and so on. In fact chunk1 contains the earliest 10% of posts written by users and chunk2 the second earliest 10% and so on. This organization is illustrated in The dataset is highly unbalanced as the ratio of depressed to non-depressed users is $83/403 = 0.205$. Clearly the depressed users constitute the minority class which makes the task of learning and predicting depressed class users quite challenging. Note that we can easily obtain the complete document for any user by concatenating

5.2 Data Preprocessing

The preprocessing involved extracting text from the $\langle \text{IT LE} \rangle$ and $\langle \text{EXT} \rangle$ XML tags. Two versions of the dataset, DS were considered for experiments. DS_{text} which included information from the $\langle \text{EXT} \rangle$ tag only. DS_{text+titles} which concatenated the text from the $\langle \text{IT LE} \rangle$ tag and $\langle \text{EXT} \rangle$ tag. The vocabulary (V) size of DS_{text+titles} is $|V| = 6,76,305$. Prior to feature extraction by

building document representations we have chosen to limit the size of the vocabulary —V — by considering the top k most frequent tokens in V that appear in DStext+titles. We have considered limiting —V — to the following sizes [3000, 10,000, 20,000, 30,000, 40,000, 50,000]. In some experiments we have also considered removing stop words such as “the”, “to”, “a” etc. by excluding tokens that had a frequency greater than 14, 000. The upper bound of 14, 000 was arrived upon by observing the frequency distribution of all tokens in the vocabulary, V

6.0 Result and Discussion

In this study, the test was performed on a data set consisting of 03 characteristics (columns) and records use different classification algorithms (logistic regression and NB) applied to the given data set. Basically, the algorithm works well to detect the depression predicted from this study. Different tests are done to check if the person is depressed. Metrics such as accuracy score, precision, re measured. The ROC receiver operating curve is observed for the classifiers. In this study, the accuracy of different logistic regression classifiers with 97%, naive with 96%. Among all classifiers compared to other measures such as accuracy, recall, f1 score, support, and logistic regression, the performance outperformed with high predictability of depression

7.0 Conclusion

This paper defines a binary classification problem as identifying whether a person is depressed, based on his tweets and Twitter profile activity. Different machine learning algorithms are exploited and different feature datasets are explored. Many preprocessing steps are performed, including data preparation and aligning, data labeling, and feature extraction and selection. The logistic model has achieved optimal accuracy metric combinations; it converts an extremely nonlinear classification problem into a linearly separable problem. Although the DT model is comprehensive and follows understandable steps, it can fail if exposed to brand-new data. This study can be considered as a step toward building a complete social media-based

platform for analyzing and predicting mental and psychological issues and recommending solutions for these users. The main contribution of this study lies in exploiting a rich, diverse, and discriminating feature set that contains both tweet text and behavioral trends of different users. This study can be extended in the future by considering more ML models that are highly unlikely to over-fit the used 15 data and find a more dependable way to measure the features’ impact.

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